

Automated Reasoning for the Andrews-Curtis Conjecture

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Abstract

We present recent developments in the applications of automated theorem proving and disproving in the investigation of the Andrews-Curtis conjecture. We answer negatively open question from [10] on extensions of AC-transformations and demonstrate trivializations of the cases reported in *op.cit.* We outline further directions of the research on the borders between Mathematics, Automated Reasoning and, more generally, AI.

Introduction and Outline

The Andrews-Curtis conjecture is a well-known open conjecture [1] in low-dimensional topology and combinatorial group theory. In terms of the latter it states that every balanced presentation of the trivial group can be transformed into a trivial one by a series of simple transformations including Nielsen transformations and conjugations of relators. Many authors expressed belief that ACC is likely to be false and there are series of trivial group presentations for which conjectured trivializations remain unknown. Various computational techniques have been applied for the search of the required trivializations (i.e. for elimination of potential counterexamples for ACC), including the methods from *computational group theory* [2]; *genetic algorithms* [9, 11, 5]; *systematic breadth-first search algorithms* [3] to name a few.

In [6, 7] we have proposed to use automated deduction in first-order logic in the search of trivializations and have shown that the approach is very competitive. It was able to trivialize any known to us example tackled by any alternative method reported in the literature, and in [7] we demonstrated new examples of simplifications, including for group presentations of dimension¹ 3 and 4. In our approach we formalized the AC transformations (commonly presented at the meta-level) at the object level of term rewriting (modulo group theory) and first-order deduction. The problem of finding AC-simplifications is reduced here to the problem of proving first-order formulae, which is then delegated to the available automated theorem provers. We also have shown that the disproving by automated finite countermodel finding can be used to show the impossibility of trivializations by subsystems of AC transformations.

In recent work [10]² the authors proposed a novel algorithmic approach to AC simplifications which relies on the use of generalized moves and a strong equivalence relation on group presentations. Further they have shown that for famous open series of Akbulut-Kirby presentations $AK(n), n \geq 3$ extending the AC rules by automorphisms of free group F_2 does not increase the sets of reachable presentations. They notice that in general “It is not known if adding these transformations to AC-moves results in an equivalent system of transformations or not”.

In this paper:

- We answer the open question from [10] negatively, that is adding automorphic transformations to AC rules leads indeed to non-equivalent systems of transformations. We utilize the approach from [7] and use automated disproving by finite countermodel finding (see the Appendix)

¹that is the number of generators (= number of relators for balanced presentations)

²which we neglected to refer to and compare with in [7]

- We show that all 12 novel AC trivialization cases reported in [10], Table 4 can also be tackled by our automated theorem proving method³, keeping our general claim alive: “finding trivializations by automated theorem proving is at least as good as by any known alternative algorithmic method”.
- We report that we failed to find⁴ AC-transformations from trivial group presentations to their images under F_2 automorphisms, reported in [10], Table 3, by our automated theorem proving method. That means that unlike for trivializations finding general AC-transformations by generic theorem proving may not be that efficient as by specialized methods of [10].

Discussion

We have shown that generic automated first-order proving and disproving can be used in combinatorial group theory, both in tackling open questions and as a competitive alternative to specialized algorithms. That places the reported research at the borders between Mathematics, Automated Reasoning and more generally, Artificial Intelligence. Further directions include development of automated extraction of the simplifying move sequences from proofs; machine learning applied to AC-proofs, in a spirit of, for example [4]; investigation of how first-order proving and disproving methods and strategies affect the efficiency of automated reasoning in this area.

References

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³proofs available online at www.csc.liv.ac.uk/~alexei/PU-cases.zip

⁴with the timeout 1000s

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Appendix

Preliminaries

For a group presentation $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n \mid r_1, \dots, r_m \rangle$ with generators x_i , and relators r_j , consider the following transformations.

AC1 Replace some r_i by r_i^{-1} .

AC2 Replace some r_i by $r_i \cdot r_j$, $j \neq i$.

AC3 Replace some r_i by $w \cdot r_i \cdot w^{-1}$ where w is any word in the generators.

Two presentations g and g' are called *Andrews-Curtis equivalent* (*AC-equivalent*) if one of them can be obtained from the other by applying a finite sequence of transformations of the types (AC1) - (AC3).

A group presentation $g = \langle x_1, \dots, x_n \mid r_1, \dots, r_m \rangle$ is called *balanced* if $n = m$, that is the number of generators is the same as the number of relators. We call such n the *dimension* of g and denote it by $Dim(g)$. Here we consider only the case of $Dim(g) = 2$ and assume the generators are a_1 and a_2 (or a and b).

Conjecture 1 (Andrews-Curtis [1]). *If $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n \mid r_1, \dots, r_n \rangle$ is a balanced presentation of the trivial group it is AC-equivalent to the trivial presentation $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n; x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle$.*

Let T_G be the equational theory of groups defined by the following equations in a vocabulary (\cdot, r, e) (for multiplication, inverse and identity, respectively).

- $(x \cdot y) \cdot z = x \cdot (y \cdot z)$
- $x \cdot e = x$
- $e \cdot x = x$
- $x \cdot r(x) = e$

In [7] we formulated ACT_2 a term rewriting system modulo T_G ⁵, which captures AC-transformations of presentations of dimension 2. The corresponding rewrite relation $\rightarrow_{ACT/G}$ captures adequately the notion of AC-rewriting, that is for presentations p_1 and p_2 we have $p_1 \rightarrow_{AC}^* p_2$ iff $t_{p_1} \rightarrow_{ACT/G}^* \cdot$. Here t_p denotes a term encoding of a presentation p , that is for $p = \langle a_1, a_2 \mid t_1, t_2 \rangle$ we have $t_p = f(t_1, t_2)$, where f is a dummy term constructor used to represent the pairs of its arguments.

Further in [7] we simplified ACT_2 and translated it to an equational theory E_{ACT_2} which includes group axioms T_G and the following axioms: $f(x, y) = f(r(x), y)$; $f(x, y) = f(x \cdot y, y)$; $f(x, y) = f(x, y \cdot x)$; $f(x, y) = f((a_i \cdot x) \cdot r(a_i), y)$ for $a_i \in A, i = 1, 2$, where $A = \{a_1, a_2\}$ is the set of generators. \tilde{E}_{ACT_2} is a modification of E_{ACT_2} where “ground conjugation” axioms $f(x, y) = f((a_i \cdot x) \cdot r(a_i), y)$ are replaced by a non-ground version $f(x, y) = f((v \cdot x) \cdot r(v), y)$.

Proposition 1. [7] *For ground terms t_1 and t_2 $t_1 \rightarrow_{ACT_2/G}^* t_2$ iff $E_{ACT_2} \vdash t_1 = t_2$ iff $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \vdash t_1 = t_2$.*

Thus E_{ACT_2} (and \tilde{E}_{ACT_2}) axiomatizes AC-equivalence, that is a presentation $g_1 = \langle a_1, a_2 \mid r_1, r_2 \rangle$ is AC-equivalent to $g_2 = \langle a_1, a_2 \mid s_1, s_2 \rangle$ iff $E_{ACT_2} \vdash f(r_1, r_2) = f(s_1, s_2)$ iff $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \vdash f(r_1, r_2) = f(s_1, s_2)$.

⁵Erratum: in [7] we erroneously missed one axiom for groups, that is $e * x = x$ (as opposed to $x * e = x$ only). That did not affect the arguments and the correct axiomatization was used in the reported in [7] experiments

Automorphism moves

In [10] it was proposed to extend AC-moves by adding automorphisms of F_2 (free group with two generators) to the set of moves. The following three moves correspond to generators of $Aut(F_2)$:

AT1 Replace \bar{r} by $\phi_1(\bar{r})$, where $\phi_1(\dots)$ is an automorphism defined by $a \mapsto a$ and $b \mapsto b^{-1}$.

AT2 Replace \bar{r} by $\phi_2(\bar{r})$, where $\phi_2(\dots)$ is an automorphism defined by $a \mapsto a$ and $b \mapsto b * a$.

AT3 Replace \bar{r} by $\phi_3(\bar{r})$, where $\phi_3(\dots)$ is an automorphism defined by $a \mapsto b$ and $b \mapsto a$.

It is known that adding these moves to AC does not increase the sets of reachable presentations when: 1) they are applied to AC-trivializable presentations (easy to see); 2) they are applied to Akbulut-Kirby presentations $AK(n), n \geq 3$ (not known to be trivializable)[10]. The general case was left open in [10]:

It is not known if adding these transformations to AC-moves results in an equivalent system of transformations or not ...

We answer the question negatively and show that adding *any* AT move to AC transformations does indeed lead to a non-equivalent system of transformations (even when applied to balanced presentations):

Theorem 1. *A group presentation $g = \langle a, b \mid aba, bba \rangle$ is not AC -equivalent to either of*

- $g_1 = \langle a, b \mid \phi_1(aba), \phi_1(bba) \rangle \equiv \langle a, b \mid ab^{-1}a, b^{-1}b^{-1}a \rangle$
- $g_2 = \langle a, b \mid \phi_2(aba), \phi_2(bba) \rangle \equiv \langle a, b \mid abaa, babaa \rangle$

A group presentation $g' = \langle a, b \mid aaba, bba \rangle$ is not AC -equivalent to

- $g_3 = \langle a, b \mid \phi_3(aaba), \phi_3(bba) \rangle \equiv \langle a, b \mid bbab, aab \rangle$

Proof we use Proposition 1 and show that $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \not\vdash t_g = t_{g_i} \ i = 1, 2$ and $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \not\vdash t_{g'} = t_{g_3}$. For each case we have applied an automated finite model finder Mace4 [8] which has found the following countermodels⁶.

1) For $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \not\vdash f((a * b) * a, (b * b) * a) = f((a * r(b)) * a, (r(b) * r(b)) * a)$:

```
interpretation( 3, [number = 1,seconds = 0], [
  function(*(_,_), [
    2,0,1,
    0,1,2,
    1,2,0]),
  function(a, [0]),
  function(b, [0]),
  function(e, [1]),
  function(r(_), [2,1,0]),
  function(f(_,_), [
    0,0,0,
    0,1,0,
    0,0,0])]).
```

⁶available online at www.csc.liv.ac.uk/~alexei/countermodels.zip

2) For $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \not\models f((a * (b * a)) * a, ((b * a) * (b * a)) * a)$: the same as above.

3) For $\tilde{E}_{ACT_2} \not\models f((a * (a * b)) * a, (b * b) * a) = f((a * (a * b)) * a, (b * b) * a) = f((b * (b * a)) * b, (a * a) * b)$:

```
interpretation( 5, [number = 1,seconds = 0], [
  function(*(_,_), [
    4,3,0,2,1,
    3,0,1,4,2,
    0,1,2,3,4,
    2,4,3,1,0,
    1,2,4,0,3]),
  function(a, [0]),
  function(b, [1]),
  function(e, [2]),
  function(r(_), [3,4,2,0,1]),
  function(f(_,_), [
    0,0,0,0,0,
    0,0,0,0,0,
    0,0,1,0,0,
    0,0,0,0,0,
    0,0,0,0,0])]).
```

□

Notice that both presentations g and g' above are of non-trivial groups. Proving similar theorem for a balanced presentation of the *trivial* group would disprove the original Andrews-Curtis conjecture; it is known though that it is not possible to do using *finite* countermodels.